

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the eighth regular issue of 2022. In this issue, 4 papers cover various topical aspects of computer science by 12 authors from 5 countries. In an ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends.

As always, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for their extremely valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, sustain the quality of our journal.

In the second regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 4 accepted articles: Sanam Fida, Nayyer Masood and Nirmal Tariq from Pakistan, and Faiza Qayyum from the Republic of Korea address in their joint research a novel hybrid ensemble clustering technique for student performance prediction. In a research collaboration between India and Greece, Banani Ghose, Zeenat Rehena and Leonidas Anthopoulos discuss a Deep Learning-based technique for predicting air quality using influencing pollutants of neighboring locations in a smart city environment. Marloes Vredenburg, Daan Sutmuller, Mariëlle den Hengst-Bruggeling, and Judith Masthoff from the Netherlands introduce an exploratory study on a system to reduce information overload and tunnel vision in homicide investigations. And last but not least, Wim Westera from the Netherlands presents three computational scoring models that take into account the number of attempts that a player makes to be successful.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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